

OPEN EARTH MONITOR

D4.1 Implementation plan and general strategy for in-situ data

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Executive summary

In the context of the Open Earth Monitor Cyberinfrastructure (OEMC) Horizon 2020 project, a set of in-situ datasets have been proposed and identified, that are relevant for the overall goal of the project, support some of the monitors defined in the WP5 (EU scale) and WP6 (Global scale), and are meaningful in the environmental domain. This document lists the datasets that have been selected so far (May 2024), and those that are under evaluation, summarising their main characteristics (including which of the monitors are planning to use or possibly going to use them), the advancements carried on by the WP4 team for each of them since the project start, and potential future steps to be taken to complete the task of making them fully available in respect of the principles of the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability). Even though there is today increasingly more environmental in-situ data available, accessing, importing and combining in-situ data is not trivial and a lot of complexity comes also from variable data licenses and terms of use including privacy and land owner rights issues.

Method & Materials

In-situ datasets are crucial for the OEMC project, as they support the monitors developed in the OEMC infrastructure, providing ground-reference data for validation of models, calibration of satellite images, and representing valuable insights on a given point area. Datasets are retrieved by the WP4 of the project: they can be produced directly, or discovered by the responsible teams. They have to be 1. Relevant; 2. open+FAIR; 3. Useful for the project. Some pre-processing may have been necessary to make them fully respect point 2 and 3. Depending on their origin, format, and status, they can be available in a native platform, or be uploaded by the responsible WP4 person into a dedicated Zenodo account. Options for their visualization are still under discussion and will be developed for the observations where a visualization is relevant and useful. All the available datasets will be listed on a dedicated STAC catalog (<https://STAC.openlandmap.org> for global data) with the links for the access (under construction). When the datasets are retrievable from a proprietary platform, a short description and the instruction on how to download them and the corresponding metadata will be provided through a computational notebook, which is under preparation.

The general workflow used in the OEMC project to produce Analysis-Ready in-situ datasets includes:

1. **Explore and describe data:** Test importing data; determine if the data is dense in space or in time and if it is based on regular or irregular entities; determine if the observations refer to points, areas (polygons) or bodies (3D). Determine the total size of data and level of Analysis-Readiness. Determine if the data is served via an efficient API following OGC / Semantic web specifications, or only a copy of the data is provided as a Zip file or similar.
2. **Produce a plan of import, bind and compression:** evaluate the needs and where useful design output format of data and the targeted output format: aim for Cloud-optimized formats of data such as [Geoparquet](#), [Flatgeobuf](#) or similar, taking into consideration the importance to not duplicate efforts already ongoing at the observations origin (data collectors and their databases) and evaluating possible implementations in the current data distribution portals/systems. Estimate size of the output data and consider subsetting data into multiple files. Consider how to boost data usability (high level of ARD) and access (best compression).
3. **Run import, bind and compression & publish data (when applicable):** produce Analysis-Ready data to serve WP5 and WP6; subset to best data i.e. remove any actual / potential artifacts. Register produced data with a DOI and/or via <https://beta.source.coop/> ([Stanimirova et al., 2023](#)) or similar (e.g. OpenLandMap.org S3); register data in the STAC (catalog) and provide minimum previews and metadata.
4. **Publish the code you developed to produce Analysis-Ready data:** best as computational notebooks (see e.g. https://github.com/Open-Earth-Monitor/Global_FAPAR_250m; [Hacklaender et al., 2023](#)); provide simple tutorials on how to use the data (make the data FAIR); demonstrate that the data can be used for operational modeling / mapping;
5. **Track usage and downloads of data and run maintenance:** follow-up user feedback and issues (if any); provide support and fix eventual problems openly via Github / Gitlab.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101059548.

Fig: Example GEDI data set (about 180 million points) subset/filtered to the best data and converted to FGB format. This data set is now available to the whole consortium for testing / modeling.

Name l2a.gedi_filtered_20190418_20221221_go_epsg.4326_egm.2008_v20231002 – gedi_v1

Source [/vsicurl/http://s3.eu-central-1.wasabisys.com/gedi-ard/l2a.gedi_filtered_20190418_20221221_go_epsg.4326_egm.2008_v20231002.fgb|layername=gedi_v1](http://s3.eu-central-1.wasabisys.com/gedi-ard/l2a.gedi_filtered_20190418_20221221_go_epsg.4326_egm.2008_v20231002.fgb|layername=gedi_v1)

Provider ogr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101059548.

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WorldCereal open global harmonized reference data repository

Published February 7, 2023 | Version 1.0.0

Dataset Open

WorldCereal open global harmonized reference data repository (CC-BY-NC licensed data sets)

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Show affiliations

Within the **ESA funded** WorldCereal project we have built an open harmonized reference data repository at global extent for model training or product validation in support of land cover and crop type mapping. Data from 2017 onwards were collected from many different sources and then harmonized, annotated and evaluated. These steps are explained in the harmonization protocol (10.5281/zenodo.7584463). This protocol also clarifies the naming convention of the shape files and the WorldCereal attributes (LC, CT, IRR, valtime and sampleID) that were added to the original data sets.

This publication includes those harmonized data sets of which the original data set was published under the CC-BY-NC license or a license similar to CC-BY-NC. See document "_In-situ-data-World-Cereal - license - CC-BY-NC.pdf" for an overview of the original data sets. Currently this publication only includes a few small data sets for Tanzania originating from a disease monitoring program of the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT). CIMMYT made more data available for countries like Kenya, Ethiopia, Rwanda and, Malawi. However due project constraints these data sets were not yet harmonized.

Files

Fig: Example of an in-situ data set (fully funded by ESA), but available only under NC license (i.e. not an open data). Although the project is global and there is a lot of point data "behind the scene", only a portion of the data has been made available and under restricted license. The output product of the World Cereal mapping is however open data under CC-BY license: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7875104>.

Review of in-situ datasets status

#1	Turbulent Fluxes of Green House Gases and Energy
Short description	Half-hourly eddy covariance fluxes and their quality flags, when present, in most cases comprehensive of storage fluxes and footprint information, calculated by the station teams and/or network facilities. Most relevant variables in the dataset are: carbon dioxide (CO ₂) flux, sensible heat flux, H ₂ O molar fraction, latent heat flux,

	CO2 storage flux, eddy covariance momentum flux, friction velocity, net ecosystem exchange, CO2 mixing ratio and the main meteorological variables
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	Available datasets from different international networks worldwide identified as relevant for the project (ICOS, AmeriFlux, NEON, TERN, eLTER, CERN, FLUXNET) with non-standardised access
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	It gives an extended overview of GHG balance over different ecosystem types, continuously measured, and it is extremely valuable per se. In connection with WP5 and WP6, it is used in calibration and validation of models, and integrated with remote sensing products for upscaling outcomes
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SIF-based high spatial resolution GPP flux estimations
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World-carbon flux monitor

#2	Biomass reference data for global space-based data validation
<i>Short description</i>	Processed biomass plot data to provide a reference database for comparison with space-based biomass estimates at different spatial resolution and epochs. Original data sources are multiple National Forest Inventories (NFI) and research plots.
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	Global biomass maps are increasing and these maps are subject to independent map assessments using reference datasets. At the time of writing the project proposal, the dataset had unique spatial and temporal resolutions
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	A global biomass dataset with uncertainty estimates of the estimated biomass at different spatial resolution and epochs. Also comes with quality flags including local and global representativity for user information and discretion.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large-area estimation of forest carbon emissions - Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World-forest carbon emissions monitor

#3	Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) of the Copernicus Global Land Service
<i>Short description</i>	The GBOV service provides multiple years of high quality in-situ measurements (88 sites) to validate 7 core land products (Top-of-canopy reflectances, Surface albedo, fAPAR, LAI, fCover, Land Surface Temperature and Soil Moisture)
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	For Copernicus Land Monitoring Services it is essential to have a series of independent validation points to ensure quality and consistency of the derived products. These data is currently available via: https://gbov.land.copernicus.eu/ ¹
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset is highly suitable for automated quality control of global biophysical indices and this is an example of how to provide ALL reference in-situ points at one central place available for viewing, importing and downloading.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global EO data to support monitoring livestock and grasslands / pastures - Tropical deforestation and characterisation tool - Tools and data for improved biomass estimation
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World-land degradation neutrality monitor - Tropical-crop monitor - World-reforestation monitor

#4	Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey (LUCAS) datasets
<i>Short description</i>	European Commission organizes every 2-3 yrs a systematic ground survey of EU countries collecting data on land use / land cover, soil samples (about 20,000 sites) and similar
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	LUCAS project (LUCAS ground surveys; https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas) is among the best organized surveys conducted across the EU (since 2006). These have generated hundreds of thousands of observations including on land cover, land use, soil properties, land degradation indices.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The LUCAS points can be used to generate train Machine Learning models to help update the CORINE land cover and similar reference products, but in a fully automated way. OpenGeoHub has been maintaining https://EcoDataCube.eu which is largely based on the LUCAS points (Witjes et al., 2022).

¹ The service has been unstable unfortunately / the website was down during the writing of report.

<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU soil observatory farmer alert system- Forest management & tracking tools for Croatia- EU constructions tracking system in forests
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-reforestation planner tool- EU-soil monitor- EU-crop monitor

#5	Snow cover in the European Alps
<i>Short description</i>	Station observations of snow depth and depth of snowfall.
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	Observed snow depth trends in the European Alps available for the period 1971 to 2019.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	Snow depth observations for the Province of Bolzano are integrated in the method to reconstruct Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) in WP5
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- High resolution SWE in selected mountain regions
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-snow monitor

#6	World Cereal Data Module
<i>Short description</i>	The dataset includes 75M features (polygons/points), including crop types for wheat and maize (https://esa-worldcereal.org/en/about/reference-data)
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	This citizen science data already existed as a public collection at the beginning of the project. The datasets are given in a shapefile as single points collected with the opportunistic sampling approach along roads and tracks.

<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	These comprehensive data can be useful for training and validation of potential OEMC machine learning models for mapping cropland, crop types, and cropping practices in the tropics.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	- Crop yield monitoring system for Africa
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	- EU-crop monitor - Tropical-crop monitor

#7	The BioTIME database
<i>Short description</i>	The database BioTIME is designed especially for scientific synthesis studies with research questions about global biodiversity. The database contains tables on species abundances across time and space, as well as important metadata about the taxa, habitat, and sampling methods. This is all made possible by data contributors
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset was not yet inventoried and used by the LifeWatch community for application purposes at the time of the proposal
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset is crucial for assessing global biodiversity trends, as it contains a wealth of repeated historical observations collected in situ. These observations provide invaluable data, enabling researchers to track changes in species distributions, population sizes, and ecosystem health over time. By analyzing this extensive information, scientists can identify patterns and trends, make informed conservation decisions, and develop strategies to protect and preserve biodiversity worldwide.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	- Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales - Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	- EU-coastal monitor - EU-biodiversity monitor

#8	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) points
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<i>Short description</i>	High resolution laser ranging observations of the 3D structure of the Earth. Millions of points with diversity of variables covering latitudes up to 50 degree north
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	Original data, available at https://gedi.umd.edu/data/download/ under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) License v4.0, were more than 20 TB in size.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset serves for global terrain and canopy height mapping, and also a source of local/regional modeling.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global topographic and hydrological service - Global monitoring system for livestock and grasslands / pastures
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-flood monitor - World-flood risk monitor

#9	Global Distribution of Seagrasses
<i>Short description</i>	This dataset shows the global distribution of seagrasses, and is composed of two subsets of point and polygon occurrence data. The data were compiled by UNEP World Conservation Monitoring Centre in collaboration with many collaborators (e.g. Frederick Short of the University of New Hampshire), organisations (e.g. the OSPAR Convention for the Northeast Atlantic sea), and projects (e.g. the European project Mediterranean Sensitive Habitats "Mediseh"), across the globe
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset was not yet inventoried and used by the LifeWatch community for application purposes at the time of the proposal
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset serves as a valuable source of in situ information on biodiversity and plays a crucial role in providing estimates of primary productivity related to benthic macroalgae components.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales - Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-coastal monitor - EU-biodiversity monitor

#10	Macroalgal canopy cover (Essential Ocean Variable) in Europe - points (2021) and polygons (2019)
<i>Short description</i>	This layer shows the current known extent and distribution of macroalgal canopy in European waters, collated by EMODnet Seabed Habitats. The polygons portion was last updated in 2019. The points were added in Sept 2021. The purpose was to produce a data product that would provide the best compilation of evidence for the essential ocean variable (EOV) known as Macroalgal canopy cover and composition (sub-variable: Areal extent), as defined by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). Kelp and furoid brown algae are the dominant species that comprise macroalgal forests.
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset was not yet inventoried and used by the LifeWatch community for application purposes at the time of the proposal
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset serves as a valuable source of in situ information on biodiversity and plays a crucial role in providing estimates of primary productivity related to benthic macroalgae components.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales- Development of EU-biodiversity monitor
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-coastal monitor- EU-biodiversity monitor

#11	Global Distribution of the Kelp Biome
<i>Short description</i>	Laminarian kelp biome. This was modelled using 44,265 cleaned primary occurrence records from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) and 13 environmental variables from the Global Marine Environment Datasets (GMED)
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset was not yet inventoried and used by the LifeWatch community for application purposes at the time of the proposal.

<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The dataset serves as a valuable source of in situ information on biodiversity and plays a crucial role in providing estimates of primary productivity related to benthic macroalgae components.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales - Development of EU-biodiversity monitor
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-coastal monitor - EU-biodiversity monitor

#12	TreeTalker
<i>Short description</i>	Hourly data of tree scale eco-physiological parameters (sap flow, stem radial growth, canopy transmitted light spectrum, stem water content and temperature) and microclimatic information
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	Data being collected since 2019 at several operational forest sites in Italy (structured network – about 500 devices) and in Europe. Data processing and curation not yet standardized at the time of the proposal.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	TreeTalker data are relevant to investigate trees' biological processes (primary productivity, transpiration) and microclimate providing an in-situ reference for models calibration and validation and ground truth for EO data. Granular TT data are suitable to quantify the small-scale spatial variability of the measured variables within a forested area.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU constructions tracking system in forests
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-forest management tool / aims at forestry, water and climate related monitors

#13	Land Use and land Cover Reference Data for Europe
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<i>Short description</i>	This data set will be sampled from the change layers of CORINE land cover between 2000 and 2018 and verified for change using the IIASA Geo-Wiki validation platform
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset did not exist at the beginning of the project, and IIASA is currently collecting it.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	The data will provide manually validated LULC changes and such dataset could be relevant for training an OEMC machine learning or another method for monitoring biodiversity state and change.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Development of EU-biodiversity monitor- Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-biodiversity monitor

#14	Drivers of Biomass Change
<i>Short description</i>	Pixel-based information collected through expert visual interpretation of very high-resolution time series of images and NDVI
<i>State-of-the-art at the proposal</i>	The dataset did not exist at the beginning of the project, and IIASA is currently collecting it.
<i>Reasons for inclusion</i>	Labeled pixels with drivers of biomass change are necessary for interpreting and understanding processes causing deforestation in Europe. Thus, it was anticipated that the data could be used for the OEMC EU forest disturbance monitor.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-rapid forest disturbance monitoring tool- EU reforestation tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-rapid forest disturbance monitor

Results & conclusions

A summary of the most relevant characteristics of each of the in-situ datasets available are provided in the following. A link to the database where the datasets are stored is also provided, when available. Links may be subject to change in the case they are updated, or accessibility is improved with time. The achievements reached since the beginning of the project are also reported, together with a plan for future actions. It has to be noted that the in-situ datasets list and the corresponding catalog are dynamic: new datasets can be discovered with time, both already existing or created lately; new methods to improve quality can be conceived; the continuous datasets will grow with time (improved quantity); improved requirements of accessibility may be implemented.

#1	Turbulent Fluxes of Green House Gases and Energy
<i>Duration</i>	from 1 to >25 years, depending on the site
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	30 minutes.
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Je3fb4hh0hvPJGDqF5y8aTdfGy4hqvOSlqVyY2PvnLw/edit?usp=sharing- https://drive.google.com/file/d/1EWbsBVvysk9sCD1nDN23ZwPTzcXRecTd/view?usp=share_link
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://data.icos-cp.eu/portal/#%7B%22filterCategories%22%3A%7B%22project%22%3A%5B%22icos%22%5D%2C%22level%22%3A%5B1%2C%22%5D%2C%22stationclass%22%3A%5B%22ICOS%22%5D%2C%22theme%22%3A%5B%22ecosystem%22%5D%7D%7D
<i>Observation area</i>	10-1000 m
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- ICOS, AmeriFlux, OzFlux + other organisations
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Increased number of stations.- Agreement among networks for standardising the access (FLUXNET Shuttle)
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Implementation of the Shuttle platform (new access)- Keep the number of stations growing (also past data, e.g. opening licenses)

<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Simone Sabbatini - CMCC

#2	Biomass reference data for global space-based data validation
<i>Duration</i>	2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0034425722000311#f0010 (will be updated once preprint of research data descriptor is already ready)
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	wur-agb-reference-database - S3 bucket S3 eu-central-1 (amazon.com) (will be updated soon with the Zenodo link)
<i>Observation area</i>	100-1000 m
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	ESA CCI biomass project / GFZ
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	New reference plots added, in particular to improve representativeness of critical, under-sampled areas (boreal forests, mountainous tropics and mangroves). Multi-resolution (500m, 1km, 10km, 25km) and multi-date (2005 2010 2015 2020) outputs have been achieved.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Yearly updates, integrate internal validation of national users that cannot share data.- To be published as research data (Under preparation)- License to be extended after publication

<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	Restricted access
<i>Responsible</i>	Martin Herold - GFZ

#3	Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) of the Copernicus Global Land Service
<i>Duration</i>	2014–2020
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	The service is currently offline.
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://land.copernicus.eu/global/gbov/
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	ACRI-ST
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	
<i>Achievements</i>	
<i>Plan for the future</i>	
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	

<i>Responsible</i>	Tom Hengl - OGH
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#4	Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey (LUCAS) datasets
<i>Duration</i>	2009–2022+
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	regular every 3 yrs
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://geoforall.fsv.cvut.cz/st_lucas/
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4740690 Landa, M., Brodský, L., Halounová, L., Bouček, T., & Pešek, O. (2022). Open Geospatial System for LUCAS In Situ Data Harmonization and Distribution. ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information, 11(7), 361. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11070361
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	EU JRC
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Continental
<i>Achievements</i>	This data set was used to produce automated CORINE LULC at 30-m spatial resolution as described in Witjes et al., (2022).
<i>Plan for the future</i>	LUCAS points are currently being combined with the https://www.eurocrops.tum.de/ to produce training points to map (seasonal, annual) distribution of land cover + main 26 crop-types. Legend and training data have already been constructed for this purpose.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY

<i>Responsible</i>	Tom Hengl - OGH
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#5	Snow cover in the European Alps
<i>Duration</i>	varying - 2021
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://clirsnow.netlify.app/dash-results/dash-climatology.html#in-situ-snow-depth
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	http://meteobrowser.eurac.edu/app_direct/meteobrowser/?inputs_&sidebarCollapsed=false&language=%22de%22&sidebarItemExpanded=null
<i>Observation area</i>	Alps
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	various organisations
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Not regular
<i>Achievements</i>	The dataset has been partially updated, in detail the data available from the Province of Bolzano. This has been done also to satisfy the needs of the connected monitor in WP5. An API is available to openly access the data of the Province (see https://github.com/GiulioGenova/MeteoBrowser).
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Update the dataset following the needs of WP5.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY-4.0 (where not stated otherwise)
<i>Responsible</i>	Valentina Premier - EURAC

#6	World Cereal Data Module
<i>Duration</i>	2016-2021
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://worldcereal-rdm.geo-wiki.org/collections/
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://worldcereal-rdm.geo-wiki.org/collections/
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	various organizations (ESA, IIASA, etc.)
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	As the dataset was available and accessible since the beginning, it was included in the internal OEMC list of In-Situ data and described there with some OEMC-relevant metadata to raise the interest of the monitors of the project. The EU-crop monitor already confirmed to be interested to use this dataset, while communication with Tropical-crop monitor and related use case leaders is ongoing.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Inclusion of the dataset in the OEMC in-situ data catalogue
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	MILENKOVIC Milutin - IIASA

#7	The BioTIME database
<i>Duration</i>	1874-2016
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://biotime.st-andrews.ac.uk
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/5026943
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	BioTIME is hosted and based at the University of St Andrews. It grew out of two ERC grants (AdG BioTIME 250189 and PoC BioCHANGE 72744) awarded to Professor Anne Magurran.
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	The dataset provided is the result of a pre-processing and filtering activity following the requirements of the interested monitors (see Methods & Materials section). Additionally, the dataset has been included in the first release of the open STAC catalog of the OEMC project.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Integrating the dataset with data from regions currently underrepresented, such as the Mediterranean basin, would enhance its comprehensiveness and utility.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	FRANCESCO DE LEO - LWE

#8	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) points
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<i>Duration</i>	2019-2022+
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	regular every year
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/gedi02_av002/
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://s3.eu-central-1.wasabisys.com/gedi-ard/l2a.gedi_filtered_20190418_20221221_go_epsq.4326_eqm.2008_v20231002.fgb
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	UMD
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	Creation of high-quality analysis ready cloud optimized format for vegetation and terrain mapping. The data reduces from >20TB to 4.1TB with the compression and filtration. The filtering process is scheduled in a yearly basis and data is available on OGH S3 server
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Data is under discussion to be hosted and served by the OpenEO backend. The dataset would be upgraded to optimize the partition and random access of the dataset.
<i>File format</i>	vectorial product
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Yu-feng Ho - OGH

#9	Global Distribution of Seagrasses
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<i>Duration</i>	1934-2020
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://data.unep-wcmc.org/pdfs/7/WCMC_013_014_Global_Distribution_of_Seagrasses.pdf?1617122071
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://doi.org/10.34892/x6r3-d211
<i>Observation area</i>	Point and polygon
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	UNEP-WCMC
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	After scouting several databases on biodiversity of oceans, this dataset was investigated and then selected and listed in the internal OEMC In-Situ data catalogue with relevant metadata.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Discussions are ongoing with OEMC use case and monitoring leaders to determine its potential utilization in their activities.- Contact the data producers for extension of the license
<i>File format</i>	vectorial product
<i>License</i>	https://www.unep-wcmc.org/en/general-data-license#data_policy
<i>Responsible</i>	FRANCESCO DE LEO - LWE

#10	Macroalgal canopy cover (Essential Ocean Variable) in Europe - points (2021) and polygons (2019)
<i>Duration</i>	2019-2021

<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://www.emodnet-seabedhabitats.eu/media/1626/c20190514_generating_eovs.pdf
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://files.emodnet-seabedhabitats.eu/data/MacroalgalCanopyCover_EOV_2023.zip
<i>Observation area</i>	Point and polygon
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	EMODnet Seabed Habitats
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Regional
<i>Achievements</i>	After scouting several databases on biodiversity of oceans, this dataset was investigated and then selected and listed in the internal OEMC In-Situ data catalogue with relevant metadata.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Discussions are ongoing with OEMC use case and monitoring leaders to determine its potential utilization in their activities.
<i>File format</i>	vectorial product
<i>License</i>	CC-BY 4.0
<i>Responsible</i>	FRANCESCO DE LEO - LWE

#11	Global Distribution of the Kelp Biome
<i>Duration</i>	1900-2020
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular

<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://data.unep-wcmc.org/pdfs/49/A_Modelled_Global_Distribution_of_the_Kelp_Biome_metadata.pdf?1609770367
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://wcmc.io/UniAuk-004
<i>Observation area</i>	Polygon
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	UNEP-WCMC
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Achievements</i>	After scouting several databases on biodiversity of oceans, this dataset was investigated and then selected and listed in the internal OEMC In-Situ data catalogue with relevant metadata.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Discussions are ongoing with OEMC use case and monitoring leaders to determine its potential utilization in their activities.- Contact the data producers for extension of the license
<i>File format</i>	vectorial product
<i>License</i>	https://www.unep-wcmc.org/en/general-data-license#data_policy
<i>Responsible</i>	FRANCESCO DE LEO - LWE

#12	TreeTalker
<i>Duration</i>	2019 - date
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	hourly

<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1YY-Mg1tMxsFVHilMvUJkvlOtdzCnvsyNP3Gg2tU_g/edit#gid=0
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	Data will be archived on the Zenodo repository and on the TreeTalker database
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area (tree scale)
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	FEM + NAT4 + others
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	National
<i>Achievements</i>	Design and implementation, still not finalized to date, of a database and a data processing pipeline based on open-source tools and data FAIRness principles. The processing routines include data quality screening and computation of the final variables of interest to be archived in the database.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Finalization of the database including data processing, data visualization dashboard and data export tools in order to provide the OEMC project with the datasets for 8 Italian forest sites (expected July 2024). Tentative extension of the number of sites data available by agreements with principal investigators involved in the TT monitoring network.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	The dataset will be initially shared within the OEMC project only and it will be made freely available (CC-BY) upon journal publication, expected in 2025, and anyway before the end of the project.
<i>Responsible</i>	Luca Belelli Marchesini - FEM

#13	Land Use and land Cover Reference Data for Europe
<i>Duration</i>	2000-2018

<i>Temporal resolution</i>	one dataset covering 18 year period
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	This dataset is currently being collected, and once that is finished, the spatial characteristics will be reported.
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	Zenodo (link will be available upon publication)
<i>Observation area</i>	Polygons (100 m2)
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	IIASA
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Europe
<i>Achievements</i>	The Geo-Wiki validation framework has been prepared and already more than 10K locations (CORINE pixels) are validated.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	IIASA is planning to collect more data and complete the validation with a minimum of two independent validators. The dataset will be prepared to make it FAIR and included in the OEMC in-situ catalog.
<i>File format</i>	Vector format
<i>License</i>	The data set will be made freely available upon journal publication, which is expected in the second part of 2024
<i>Responsible</i>	MILENKOVIC Milutin - IIASA

#14	Drivers of Biomass Change
<i>Duration</i>	2010-2020
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	one dataset covering a single decade

<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	This dataset is currently being collected, and once that is finished, the spatial characteristics will be reported.
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	Zenodo (link will be available upon publication)
<i>Observation area</i>	Polygon/pixel 100m
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	IIASA
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	EU-27, Russia
<i>Achievements</i>	The Geo-Wiki framework for collecting the data has been prepared and already about 4000 locations (CCIBiomass pixels) are validated.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	IIASA plans to collect at least 5000 locations and complete the validation with a minimum of two independent validators. The dataset will be prepared to make it FAIR and included in the OEMC in-situ catalogue.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	The data set will be made freely available upon journal publication, which expected at the second part of 2024
<i>Responsible</i>	MILENKOVIC Milutin - IIASA

Related tasks and outputs

In-situ datasets are a crucial aspect to give support to the monitors defined within the OEMC project. WP4 directly collaborates with WP5 and WP6 to ensure consistent and meaningful data provision to both the European- and Global-scales use-cases of the project. However, in-situ datasets are valuable products available to the scientific community *per se*, and the advantages of being part of OEMC is bidirectional: from the one side, the monitors have ground-reference info for calibration, validation and integration activities structural for their goals; on the other side, in-situ data providers gain in terms of visibility and data discovery. Least but not last, users will have easier accessibility to datasets following the FAIRness principles. In-situ datasets list is being included in a dedicated STAC catalog that will be integrated and

completed in the months to come. In this respect, a number of in-situ datasets exist that are important for some of the monitors but still under evaluation in terms of “readiness” (open license, FAIRness level, accessibility); or, they are in a good advancement state, but the interest of the monitors need to be better evaluated and confirmed. The following are the more advanced in such terms:

#I	EEA Air Quality Measurements
<i>Short description</i>	Hourly measurement values of NO ₂ , SO ₂ , O ₃ , PM ₁₀ , and PM _{2.5} from stations reported by EEA member states.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Air quality assessment at continental scale- Air quality assessment at regional scale
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	EU-air quality monitor
<i>Duration</i>	2013-2024
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	hourly
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/explore-interactive-maps/up-to-date-air-quality-data
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/content/documentation/How_To_Downloads.pdf Please note an R script is available to download parquet files of pre-processed data, increasing accessibility and reliability
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	European Environmental Agency
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Europe
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Definition of the access options and definitive format- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue

<i>File format</i>	parquet
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Johannes Heisig - IFGI

#11	Drivers of Tropical Forest Loss
<i>Short description</i>	<p>The dataset contains 1,150,000 unique locations in the tropics identifying drivers of forest loss (derived from Global Forest Watch map) between 2008 and 2019. Data were collected using Geo-Wiki and is currently hosted by IIASA.</p> <p>A new pilot campaign to support the monitoring of tropical deforestation is under consideration for this project.</p>
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterization tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	Tropical-deforestation monitor
<i>Duration</i>	2008-2019
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Regular every year
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01227-3
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	<p>Currently accessible for download from the PURE repository hosted by IIASA: 10.22022/NODES/06-2021.122. https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/17539/</p> <p>If needed, it will be made accessible from Zenodo</p>
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area

<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	IIASA
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Intercontinental (tropics)
<i>Plan for the future</i>	A new pilot campaign that could support the monitoring of tropical deforestation is under consideration for this project. Understanding the needs of the Wageningen University for their OEMC use case, in particular for the extension of the campaign to pan-tropic, and consequent inclusion of the dataset in the OEMC in-situ catalogue. The new data shall eventually be acquired with a public access license.
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	Restricted access due to some quality concerns from the first pilot test dataset, but shall be eventually public
<i>Responsible</i>	MILENKOVIC Milutin - IIASA

#III	Forest Inventory of Trento province (Trentino), Italy - InfoCarb
<i>Short description</i>	Forest Carbon Stocks in the Province of Trento inventory of Trentino based on 150 plots (15 m radius) over 6200 Km ² land area. Estimation of organic carbon pools stored above and belowground.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	None currently. Suitable for forestry related monitors.
<i>Duration</i>	2002
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kIVHNzGn7JgACTVfwXglAnNcKsNFeKD4/view?usp=share_link

<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	Data will be archived on the Zenodo repository
<i>Observation area</i>	Plot (radius: 15 m)
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	FEM - PAT (Provincia Autonoma Trento)
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	regional
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Identification of monitors and use cases interested in the dataset- Conclusion of the pre-processing activity to make the dataset FAIR- Inclusion of the dataset on Zenodo- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue- Discussion with the monitor and use cases leaders on the use of this dataset
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC BY-NC 3.0
<i>Responsible</i>	Luca Belelli Marchesini - FEM

#IV	LIDAR survey of Trento province (Trentino), Italy
<i>Short description</i>	DTM, DSF and DBM layers for the province of Trento produced by airborne LIDAR surveys
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	None currently. Suitable for forestry related monitors.
<i>Duration</i>	2006, 2014-2018

<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://siat.provincia.tn.it/stem/
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://siat.provincia.tn.it/stem/
<i>Observation area</i>	Point
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	PAT (Provincia Autonoma Trento)
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	regional
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Identification of monitors and use cases interested in the dataset- Accessibility and FAIRness assessment and possible improvements- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue- Discussion with the monitor and use cases leaders on the use of this dataset
<i>File format</i>	*.laz, *.tiff, *.txt
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Luca Belelli Marchesini - FEM

#V	PATRIS (parameterization of Trentino forest types by rapid forest inventory)
<i>Short description</i>	The dataset consists of relascope measurements and forest structure parameters (LAI, clumping index, gap fraction by zenith angle range) derived from hemispheric photos over 789 plots in the province of Trento
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	

<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	None currently. Suitable for forestry, water and climate related monitors.
<i>Duration</i>	2004-2005
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://drive.google.com/file/d/12b2N9svugGx94pNh7De2wyazZ1sJluCW/view?usp=share_link
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	Data will be archived on the Zenodo repository
<i>Observation area</i>	Plot (relascope)
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	FEM - PAT (Provincia Autonoma Trento)
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	regional
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Identification of monitors and use cases interested in the dataset- Accessibility and FAIRness assessment and possible improvements- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue- Discussion with the monitor and use cases leaders on the use of this dataset
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC BY-NC 3.0
<i>Responsible</i>	Luca Belelli Marchesini - FEM

#VI	sPlotOpen
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<i>Short description</i>	Vegetation plots (n = 95,104) recording cover or abundance of naturally co-occurring vascular plant species within delimited areas. sPlotOpen contains three partially overlapping resampled datasets (c. 50,000 plots each), to be used as replicates in global analyses. Besides geographical location, date, plot size, biome, elevation, slope, aspect, vegetation type, naturalness, coverage of various vegetation layers, and source dataset, plot-level data also include community-weighted means and variances of 18 plant functional traits from the TRY Plant Trait Database
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	EU-biodiversity monitor
<i>Duration</i>	1888-2015
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/cms/asset/29811ced-a5c8-4f1e-bfce-702b2f8f7425/geb13346-fig-0001-m.jpg
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://idata.idiv.de/ddm/Data/ShowData/3474?version=55
<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	Div
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Global
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Discussion with the monitor and use cases leaders on their requirements, in particular if they need the whole dataset or only the functional traits part- Discussion with the monitors/use cases if another similar dataset on soil macrofauna is needed- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)

<i>License</i>	CC-BY-4.0
<i>Responsible</i>	Martijn Witjes - OGH

#VII	Dataset_Biodiversity_Marine_Lifewatch_2015
<i>Short description</i>	Lifewatch ERIC provides diverse species occurrence datasets acquired by state of the art techniques such as plankton imaging and acoustic receivers.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns at national and European scales
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	EU-coastal monitor
<i>Duration</i>	2014-current
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	Depending on the monitoring network. Data relying on sea going campaigns, has a monthly or bi-monthly resolution. Sensor networks (e.g. acoustics) have continuous measurements.
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	VLIZ: https://www.lifewatch.be/en/data & https://rshiny.vsc.lifewatch.be/ Other nodes (distributed centers) will be added later.
<i>Observation area</i>	Regional
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	LifeWatch ERIC Distributed centers: VLIZ, Biopolis, NIB, SZN, HCMR.
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	Point data

<i>Plan for the future</i>	At the beginning of the project, data was acquired and maintained by multiple LifeWatch Eric distributed centers. Other LifeWatch ERIC nodes (distributed centers) will be included for data ingestion: Biopolis, NIB, SZN, HCMR. Each distributed center has its own storage solution. In this project, a selection of the most useful parameters will be made. The datasets will be converted to Darwin Core format and made available via an Integrated Publishing Toolkit. This will allow users to retrieve all data in a central repository. It is needed to understand if we can include everything under the same umbrella (dataset) or to select a subset of datasets according to the needs of the monitors/use cases. The selected datasets will then be included in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>File format</i>	Darwin Core
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Willem Boone - LWE

#VIII	LandPKS crowd-sourced observations
<i>Short description</i>	Crowdsourced observations of land cover, soil properties, land degradation; citizen-science based with over 80,000 points as in 2022.
<i>Use case(s) connected</i>	Land Degradation Neutrality tool
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	
<i>Duration</i>	2016–2022+
<i>Temporal resolution</i>	not regular
<i>Link(s) to spatial characteristics</i>	https://storage.googleapis.com/api-docs.landpotential.org/index.html
<i>Link to access the dataset</i>	https://landpotential.org/data-portal/

<i>Observation area</i>	Point area
<i>Institution code of owner of the datasets</i>	USDA-ARS
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	global
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check with the data producer the possibility to use this dataset - Discussion with the monitors and use cases leaders on their requirements - Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>File format</i>	ASCII file (*.txt, *.csv, etc.)
<i>License</i>	CC-BY
<i>Responsible</i>	Steffen Fritz - IIASA

The following datasets are under evaluation:

#IX	Global Historical Climatology Network - Daily
<i>Short description</i>	GHCN-Daily dataset integrates daily climate observations from approximately 30 different data sources.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extend the period to after 2020 - Check accessibility - Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-climate monitor - Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset

#X	European Climate Assessment & Dataset
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<i>Short description</i>	The ECA dataset contains series of daily observations at meteorological stations throughout Europe and the Mediterranean
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Extend the period to after 2020- Check accessibility- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-climate monitor- Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset

#XI	OGIMET
<i>Short description</i>	Professional information about meteorological conditions in the world
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Extend the period to after 2020- Define if R format or csv- Check accessibility- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- EU-climate monitor- Global ML-based gridded meteo dataset

#XII	NEON Plant foliar traits
<i>Short description</i>	Traits of sun-lit canopy plants reported at the level of the individual (woody plants) or community (herbaceous plants).
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Investigate accessibility and FAIRness- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	World-reforestation monitor

#XIII	International Soil Moisture Datasets
<i>Short description</i>	The International Soil Moisture Network is an international cooperation to establish and maintain a global in-situ soil moisture database.
<i>Plan for the future</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Resolve accessibility and redistribution constraints- Inclusion in the STAC in-situ catalogue
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- World-Drought Monitor- EU-drought monitor

#XIV	Geo-wiki ground observations of land cover
<i>Short description</i>	About 50,000 ground observations of land cover / land use which was used to generate global land cover maps and similar
<i>Plan for the future</i>	Agree with the monitor leaders whether this dataset is needed for their purposes or not, and in case whether or not it should be replaced by a more up-to-date product
<i>Supported monitor(s)</i>	World-land degradation neutrality monitor

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